

Cards Against Digital Humanities

participatory design game for prototyping in DH

References:

Connected-Spaces toolkit by I. Aizu, A. Delente, and A. Friedland. 2015. <http://aureliafriedland.com/filter/teaching/WORKSHOPPeople-centered-Mobility>

Critical Loop

J. T. Baccarelli. Critical loop. 2015.
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Cards against Humanity

C. A. H. LLC. Cards against humanity
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A. Burdick, J. Drucker, P. Lunenfeld, T. Presner, and J. Schnapp. *Digital Humanities*. Mit Press, 2012.

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Natural Language
Processing

Textual Analysis

Text-Mining

Quantitative Analysis

Machine Reading

Algorithmic Analysis

Mapping

Data Visualization

Information Design

Modeling Knowledge

Experiential Navigation

Scale Modeling

Geographic Information
Systems

Parametrics

algorithm design

Installation

Research

Spatial Argument

Family

Nature

National

User Communities

Large-Scale Patterns

Past

Present

Future

Far Future

**Geographic Information
Systems**

Parametrics

algorithm design

Use as Performance

Crowd-Sourcing

Collaborative
Authorship

Participatory Content
Creation

Museum

Urban Planners

Bilinguals

Policy makers

Schools

Other Dicipleans

Makers

Rich Interaction

Animated Archives

Experiential Navigation

Global Networks

Partners,
Audiences & users

Prototype

Prototype

Prototype

Prototype

Partners,
Audiences & users

Partners,
Audiences & users

Simulation
Environments

Experiential Navigation

Embodied Interface

Aggregator

Bot

Internet of Things

Oculus Rift

To create a global
networks

To explore

To be more efficient

To find help

To share experience and
knowledge

To feel part of
something

To observe

Prototype

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

To participate

To feel understood

To play

To find more information

To feel empowered

To gain awareness

Structured mark-up

Ambient data

Contactless

Bio Sensors

Text

Facial Recognition

Tracking

Sensors

Courser

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

Input/Output

Input/Output

Input/Output

User Goal

User Goal

User Goal

Input/Output

Input/Output

Input/Output

Input/Output

Input/Output

Input/Output

Touch/gestures

Eye Tracking

Kinect

Input/Output

Input/Output

Input/Output

Input/Output

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Input/Output

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Wild card

